

EFFECT OF FEEDING PLACE AND AMOUNT OF FOOD REQUIRED WITH AGE ON THE QUANTITY AND QUALITY OF WRAPPED SILKWORM COCOONS

Rakhmanova Kh.E.

Department of Sericulture and Mulberry of TSAU, Associate Professor

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Abstract. *This article provides information that the dense placement of caterpillars in the rearing area leads to damage to the cuticular layer of the skin of caterpillars, which as a result dramatically increases the spread of microorganisms, which leads to the appearance of infectious diseases.*

In such conditions, due to the increased need for food, caterpillars lagging behind in development arises. Such caterpillars are more susceptible to infectious diseases, which results in massive caterpillar infections.

Keywords: *silkworm, feeding area, productivity, mulberry leaf, agrotechnical recommendations.*

Nowadays, the new breeds and hybrids of silkworms created by our scientists differ sharply from old breeds in viability, are distinguished by a short period of feeding of worms, high viability, good food consumption and fast digestion.

However, changing the feeding area, which is considered the most important rule of agricultural technology of feeding worms, has a negative effect on the results of even newly created breeds and hybrids with high viability and productivity. Since silkworms are grown in special buildings, their place of residence is considered as a breeding ground for worms. As silkworms age, their body becomes larger and requires more area for feeding. If this agrotechnical measure is carried out incorrectly, that is, if the feeding area is less than the norm, but at the same time is not formed at the required level, then there will be fewer leaves, and the worms will settle densely and without feeding will become large and small. From age to age, silkworms saturated with food fall asleep faster than small worms that are not saturated with food, that is, the molting process begins.

Definitely, it negatively affects the incidence of silkworms with various diseases, as well as the quantity and quality of the total number of wrapped cocoons. The information obtained on this matter is presented in the table below.

The data in the table show that the feeding area and the amount of food affect the viability of the silkworm, as well as the number of cocoons and its quality indicators, if we evaluate the data obtained based on our experience. It is known that the number of rolled cocoons sharply decreases compared to the comparative variant due to a change in the number of leaves produced depending on the feeding area. At the same time, the total number of cocoons of worms of the comparative variant fed on an area of 60 m² was 90%, 82% on an area of 50 m², 72% on an area of 40 m², 60% on an area of 30 m² and 48% on an area of 20 m². These figures show that the feeding area decreases to 20-30 m² per 1 box of worms, the total number of cocoons decreases to 20-30 m² per 1 box of worms, and the number of cocoons is 30-42%. At the same time, the number

of sorted cocoons decreased by 19-29%, while the number of unsorted and poor cocoons, on the contrary, increased by 20-30%.

The effect of feeding area and amount of food on the number and quality of silkworm cocoons.

Variants	Number of collected worms	Total in package tablets		Including					
				Assorted cocoons		Unsorted cocoons		Black stripe	
		number	%	number	%	number	%	number	%
1-variant	500	240	48	156	65	77	32	7	3,0
2-variant	500	300	60	225	75	69	23	6	2,0
3-variant	500	360	72	310	86	45	12,5	5	1,5
4-variant	500	410	82	369	90	37	9,0	4	1,0
5-variant	500	450	90	423	94,0	25	5,5	2	0,5

Normal expansion of the feeding area for worms has a positive effect on the productivity and quality of cocoons. On the other hand, with a very dense arrangement of silkworms, they injure each other with their loops on false legs, and pathogenic microbes pass into the body through these injuries.

If you place a lot of leaves in a small area, a dense cover will be created that will cover the worms. As a result, air circulation between the leaves will deteriorate, the level of air humidity will increase, and worms will begin to appear. As a result, this will negatively affect the total number of wrapped cocoons.

Variants	Number of worms in one box (19 grams) pieces	Total number of wrapped cocoons %	Average weight of one cocoon	Product of cocoons from one box with worms kg
1 variant (20m ²)	45000	48	1,42	30,7
2 variant (30m ²)	45000	60	1,50	40,5
3 variant (40m ²)	45000	72	1,61	52,2
4 variant (50m ²)	45000	82	1,70	62,7
5 variant (60m ²)	45000	90	1,82	73,7

The data in the table show that a sharp decrease in the feeding area and the amount of feed supplied to it during the feeding period of the worms also led to a decrease in the total number of wrapped cocoons, the weight of 1 cocoon and the yield of worms from 1 box. For example, the total number of wrapped cocoons in the experimental variants decreases (by 48-60%), and the weight of 1 cocoon decreases sharply (1.42-1.50 g).

It can be seen that in the comparative variant with feeding with a standard feeding area and feed of the required level, 73.7 kg were obtained from 1 box of worms, when feeding worms on 50 m² this figure was 62.7 kg, when feeding worms on 40 m² - 52.2 kg, 40.5 kg when feeding on 30 m² and 20 m². When feeding on the site, the yield was 30.7 kg. Thus, the fact that the feeding area is less than the norm leads to a decrease in the yield of cocoons from 1 box of worms to 34-43 kg.

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